

The dream of immigration and selling the illusion in installments

Facebook groups are full of misinformation and no censor

Report by: Hassan Al Baiti

Recent events in the so-called "Caravan of Hope", which includes many illegal immigrants to Poland, have returned many questions related to how they received incorrect information on the subject of migration, especially since some of those who experienced this experience had their beginning on social media, although the social media policy classifies this activity as "[exploitation of human beings](#)" as it is found in the prohibitions of publishing in Meta, or the term "human trafficking" as it is found on [Twitter](#), [TikTok](#) and [Google](#). Both terms are based on the definition of the United Nations, which linked these two terms to the subject of illegal immigration, because of the search of immigrant individuals for a better life, and the end of some of them is that Yemenis continue to suffer from migration, fleeing danger to danger, as happened to some of them within the [Caravan of Hope](#), or to those who [sailed towards Greece](#). This is summarized by researcher Bojumela Hall in her report entitled "[Dreams of Yemeni Freedom](#) and [Mobility](#)", which ends with a scene in which Yemenis and others suffer from the delay in accepting or rejecting [asylum requests](#), and some of them may [die](#) indifferently from smugglers.

However, in front of this policy, we find publications in a public and private group, and in pages that refer to this matter, and may even collect information related to the identity of the browsers themselves, and this is another violation of the platform policy, which prohibits this type of publication.

There are also posts showing the extent of the [fraud](#) or fallacy to which some of those looking for a path to migration were exposed by accounts that later turned out to be fraudulent, so how were

they able to mislead the pioneers of social media platforms about the issue of migration or asylum?

Who does this work?

From what has been tracked through Facebook groups, it is noticeable that the illegal migration route may be managed by individuals known as "[smugglers](#)", or by offices claiming to provide a tourist visa to some countries with the aim of facilitating entry to the European Union countries, Canada, or any other country that each [refugee](#) aspires to enter.

During the monitoring of many groups, it was noted that some of the victims of these traffickers in the name of illegal immigration rely on sending false papers to their clients who pay their money in order to obtain the opportunity of a decent life.

On the other hand, there are those who send [assurances](#) that the payment is received after the completion of the initial procedures for accepting the asylum application, and with all this, the background of some dealers remains few on the subject of migration, to facilitate fraud against them with misleading information about it.

These publications target many areas experiencing political and security crises in the Arab world, such as Yemen, Syria, Libya, Lebanon and Iraq, and this is observed through the publications of smugglers, and the so-called offices of issuing visas and tourism.

With the huge amount of misinformation about opportunities to obtain humanitarian asylum, the [Mobile Information Team](#), a platform created by volunteers in Greece to provide correct information to those who want to seek asylum in Greece and European countries, points out facts that reveal the falsity of that misinformation on social media. For example, the platform relied on the databases of the European ministries of migration in 2018 to find out who was granted humanitarian asylum, and who were rejected from [Yemenis](#), showing that the majority of Yemenis were granted temporary protection, and few of them received humanitarian asylum.

Model of Deception

Yemenis establish some groups on Facebook in order to exchange information about the mechanism of illegal migration, or they are forced to participate in groups concerned with other relevant Arab communities.

In these groups, the method of presenting this misleading information varies from [promoting](#) an office such as [Al-Khalidi's](#), for example, which was observed in the account of Hassan Khaled Hamsho called "Abu Omar", who participates in 10 Facebook groups that revolve around immigration and asylum, where Hassan claims that he has the ability to copy European passports and residencies of similar origin that help illegal immigration. He opposed clips of some of his customers who praise his way of working, and he has a WhatsApp number that begins with the key to the state of Azerbaijan, and he follows his page on Facebook 584 accounts.

One of the [videos](#) shows how he prints a European Schengen visa with security specifications that can pass through the security screening device at airports, and proves this by turning off the lights to show the security signs on the visa.

In other [videos](#), he proves to his customers through one of the clips that the holder of the forged Danish passport was able to access and travel through airports.

When trying to verify all the videos included in his account, the first is the obvious falsification through the following, after referring to an article written by the [head](#) of the [German Identity Documentation Systems Department](#), Dr. Uwe Seidel, in response to the increasing issue of falsification in the EU visas and their residence, where he presented a sample of a European Schengen visa containing many [watermarks](#), where we compared it with the visa photographed from Hassan's account as follows:

<p>Visa with keesingte chnologies platform for document security</p>	<p>Visa from Abu Omar account</p>
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When using the [Forensic](#) feature of InVid, we found a difference between the two visas in terms of the following:

Differences:	J-one. - Where's the original?	Fraudulent Visa
The extent to which the face appears through the enhancements feature Enhancers		

على إعادة JPEG ghosts تعتمد خوارزمية: [1] تعليق عليه
 ضغط الصورة بجودة متعددة وطرح كل منها من الأصل. تتم معالجة الصور المتبقية الناتجة لاحقاً لإبراز المناطق البارزة ومن المحتمل أن مختلفة. بعد ذلك ، يتم تحديد الصور التي من JPEG تنشأ من صورة المرجح أن تحتوي على نتائج مثيرة للاهتمام (أي تلك التي تحتوي على تناقضات محلية). قد تتوافق المناطق الصفراء المتسقة على خلفية زرقاء مع آثار التلاعب ، خاصة إذا كانت لا تتوافق مع الحواف ، ولكن مع مناطق بأكملها.

Further differences between the [original](#) and [forged](#) visas can be seen through the [document testing](#) device, which shows the difference between everything that is real and forged. Otherwise, the European Union's [Europol](#) security apparatus has been active in arresting those who facilitate the smuggling of migrants with these [forged](#) visas since 2021.

There are many people like Hassan who sell the illusion by forging identity papers, IDs and visas, and they are spread in many Facebook groups, trying to delude the public that these forged papers are similar in origin and difficult to identify, as is the case with the "[passport of certificates](#)" account, and this in itself is contrary to the [publishing policy related](#) to combating fraud and deception.

However, there are those who sell it and document it in photo and video, as is the case in the group [helping Iraqis to emigrate to Europe 2022](#). This group established its Facebook page on January 11, 2022. This group is supervised by four accounts, including [two](#) accounts in the name of [Abdullah Al-Iraqi](#), who practices smuggling, promotes it through video clips, and participates in three groups. On his personal page, he notes that he is registered in his location in the Kharkiv region of Ukraine.

I explained it to him every way I know how.

In the same context, the method of putting forward misleading information may be in the form of [asking](#) members of the virtual group to receive an offer of immigration and carrying a set of misleading information that some commenters on those posts cannot refute, whether by warning the person not to take any uncalculated step.

The proposal may be in the form of a commentary on a question for any member of the group about the [method](#) of migration or asylum for any country, and here comes the dissemination of misleading information sometimes as a result of the circulation of more than one group.

While some prefer to be offered through WhatsApp and Telegram for fear of banning their promotional posts on illegal immigration, as shown in one of [them](#) commenting on a published inquiry, by including [Telegram](#) and [WhatsApp](#) links to Yemeni groups so that it facilitates communication there, as the laws of Telegram and WhatsApp do not control this type of activity.

All groups that belong to Yemenis by name or involve Yemeni accounts according to the definition of their owners were tracked. The date of creation of that group, the nature of who manages it, and the type of information published in it were monitored through the use of the search engine to search for four words: fraud, smuggling, asylum, and migration. The search results show publications or comments that contain these words. The time option was determined in 2022.

The beginning was with the [Yemeni Immigration and Asylum](#) Group, which was established on November 24, 2015, and the name changed according to Facebook's notice during 2018 from the name "Group of Distinguished Yemeni Youth and Girls" to the current name, and it is [supervised by](#) news pages on behalf of Western countries, as some of them participate in the group "[Immigration and Asylum](#)"

In this group, we found some misleading posts and comments, the first of which is with an account under a pseudonym called [Abu Shaddad](#), which promotes illegal immigration in a guaranteed manner as he described through the disputed area of Ceuta between Morocco and Spain, which is under Spanish sovereignty, asking the serious people to communicate with him through the private. When we return to what this promotion is, we find that the borders have already been opened since May 17, but we find [warnings](#) from the [Spanish](#) border guards about the flow of illegal migrants, and that border security should be strengthened with more police and civil guards, and that the Spanish authorities deported 40 Yemenis from [their territories](#) despite having asylum papers issued by the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees.

In another publication, a group of [Yemenis in the Netherlands](#) for an account called CooPer [Davi](#), claims to be a smuggler who was offered a Guatemalan passport with a stamp to leave the country, and this passport will enable him to cross to Turkey and then Europe, at a price of \$2,500. This is misleading information that carries a lot of fallacies, as this type of passport [requires](#) an investment of at least \$50,000, and a set of other internationally recognized conditions. In [another publication](#), he says that he was offered a smuggler in Turkey a visa to Canada for \$9,000 Without a fingerprint and within nine days, provided that he goes to Cairo, and submits the passport to the embassy of the Netherlands there, and here the majority of commentators agree that the matter is fraud and

outright fraud, except for one that encouraged him to do so, justifying the existence of offices that request payment after arriving in the Netherlands, and this publication carries several fallacies, as the absence of a fingerprint for this visa is considered misleading information, because the [fingerprint](#) is required for everyone over the age of 12, and only in specific cases such as government officials of countries, and those who cannot be fingerprinted for a problem on their fingers, and some smugglers try Or fake tourist offices to circumvent those looking to migrate by misleading information.

In a group of [Yemenis in the Netherlands](#) established on May 5, 2019, a publication similar to the CooPer Davi publication drew attention, although the amounts requested here differ, but the story is similar to the request to come to Egypt, as indicated by [Naji Al-Nahari](#) in his publication in the group, and among the comments that sentenced this work to fraud, there was a comment by Maher Al-Hanashli confirming the validity of this misleading information, and this method is usually followed in inflicting victims.

Regarding the Yemeni community group in Germany, [Razan Mohammed](#) addressed an inquiry about the existence of a work visa to Germany without work contracts or language, which made some commentators go to judge the publication as a type of fraud, and the other refutes the reasons for this visa as a type called "job search visa", and the other refers to the official conditions of the visa, which requires a B1 level in the German language, and to return to the published image, and by referring to the plagiarism checker to examine the text in the image, it was found that it was from another post on [Facebook](#), and in any case everything found in this post was verified to make it clear that the [job search visa](#) requires proficiency in the German language, while the [free work visa](#), which is classified as a national D visa, requires submission through German embassies around the world.

In one of the publications, a group called " Krupp Al-Hijra to Europe without Iraqi and Syrian smugglers", [Hussein Karama](#) published a method that facilitates migration by issuing him a medical report. According to this report, he does not need to make a fingerprint in a European embassy, and that the payment after arrival at the airport, and before that the person only pays the report fees of \$220, and through the official platform of the European Schengen visas for medical treatment visa procedures, it was found that there is no need to go to the embassy, and from fingerprinting.

Canada Mirage

In browsing the rest of the other groups in which Yemeni accounts are joined, we find that misleading information is colored according to the goal to which the immigrant aspires. Among those misinformation is what was published by [Ayman Suleiman](#), [Abu Abdo Al-Amir](#) and [Nun Okum](#) - from different Facebook groups - that there is a person claiming to be a Canadian lawyer who offered to submit his files to him and his family to obtain humanitarian asylum in Canada in exchange for money to be paid before going to the Canadian embassy, after the initial approval from inside Canada, or the approval of the Commission, as happened in the story of the fraud that [Abdulaziz Ali](#) was exposed to with a person named Alexander, or as mentioned by a member of the "[Canadian Asylum](#) and [Guarantees](#)" group who hid his name, as he stated that a lawyer asked him to fill out an asylum form and that he would follow it until approval is obtained.

This message itself was noticed during the writing of the report by the group "[Humanitarian Asylum for Canada](#)", which sends the WhatsApp number to a man claiming to be a Canadian lawyer named "Milad Dunkel" and was sent via WhatsApp, as it is noted that most of those who correspond prefer WhatsApp, and after correspondence and there are many examples of it in the world of social communication, we found some clear fallacies in accountability, for example, that the UNHCR does not interfere with asylum accountability directly, referring to this to communicate with the Canadian embassy as indicated in the [UNHCR's FAQ](#) platform. As for obtaining asylum for those who are outside Canada, in the [draft](#) translated into Arabic from the official platform of the Canadian government, the matter is done through the resettlement process supervised by the UNHCR, and in cooperation with the International Organization for Migration, that is not the case of an individual claiming to be a lawyer who can submit an asylum file, unless the refugee person enters Canada through land or air ports as explained in the [Canadian Red Cross guide](#).

facebook.com/groups/355127005407321/posts/1097562581163756/

بحث في فيسبوك

مناقشة العناصر المميزة الموضوعات الأعضاء الوسائط الملفات

حول المجموعة بإدارة Shimon M Odeesh

خاصة يمكن للأعضاء فقط رؤية الأعضاء الموجودين بالمجموعة وما يقومون بنشره.

مرئية يمكن لأي شخص العثور على هذه المجموعة.

تعرف على المزيد

Noon Olim
٢١ يونيو

يمكن حد يوصلني هذا الكلام صحبح احرب ولي نصب
"الترح التفضيلي بالنسبة لأمر اللجوء كاملة بحج عليك قرارة الترح بدقة
جدا"
كيفة التقديم لدينا؟
ماذا نتاح من لوثبات وأوراق؟
ماهي التكلفة للكيلف وكني يتم دفعها؟
وما المدة للسفر؟
كل هذا في هذا الترح بحج التدقيق جدا
"أولا الأوراق المطلوبة وهي":
1. صورة عي البطاقة الشخصية لكل فرد
2. صورة شخصية بخلفية بيضاء لكل فرد
3. رفاان جوال فعال
4. بريد الكتروني فعال
5. عنوان منزل دقيق
6. صورة جواز السفر أن وجد
7. تقوم بتوكلي عن تسجل مقطع فيديو مصور من خلال هاتفك المحمول
لتوكلي بأمر الملف
بتم ارسال الأوراق المطلوبة هنا عبر واتساب
"ملاحظة" ان عدم تواجد جواز السفر امر طبيعي لان الحكومة الكندية تعلم جدا
ان طالب اللجوء ليني قادر على استرجاعه لانه من الصعب عليه التواصل

تبدل المجموعات

Shimon M Odeesh
المجموعة بإدارة

اللجوء والكفالات الكندية Canadian Asylum and Sponsorship

مجموعة خاصة ٤٥٠ ألف عضو

تم الانضمام دعوة

الصفحة الرئيسية للمجتمع

العنايات

١٠٠٪

facebook.com/groups/801475643739626/posts/1133435390543648/

بحث في فيسبوك

مناقشة العناصر المميزة الموضوعات الأعضاء الوسائط الملفات

حول الوصول إلى كندا صعب وليس مستحيل فلا تأس

خاصة يمكن للأعضاء فقط رؤية الأعضاء الموجودين بالمجموعة وما يقومون بنشره.

مرئية يمكن لأي شخص العثور على هذه المجموعة.

كندا تعرف على المزيد

ابو عبد الأمير
٣ أغسطس الساعة ٤:٣٣ ص

يعطيكن العافية حبيت استشيركن
في واحد بدو يقدملي طلب لجوء
على كندا وقلي خلالا 60 يوم السفر
والدفع بعد مايقبلوني بالسفارة بدو
\$4000

١٥ تعليقًا

إرسال تعليق أعجبني

أبرز التعليقات

كيف تصل الى كندا
مجموعة خاصة ٧٩٦ ألف عضو

تم الانضمام دعوة

الصفحة الرئيسية للمجتمع

العرف

العنايات

١٠٠٪

[Amr](#) Jawahara's post and [the](#) comments on it indicate another method of fraud by tricking the person into being able to settle his file in order to emigrate without resorting to UNHCR or coming to Canadian territory through a woman named Christina, as her name appears in the e-mails Christine McAllister.

When trying to search for the content of her message, it was found that the submission form is used by a fake email members@canadianvisaexpert.net, as two submission forms were found that were sent via this email in [May](#) and [July](#) 2022.

Interestingly, the same email uses several forms of correspondence and the impersonation of other people's names, as was found in another question by [Karim Mamdouh Zaki](#) through a publication in which he published pictures of the documents in his hand, wondering about the validity of the data contained in the publication. It appears in his publication that Jessica L. Edwards contacted him in her capacity as a public relations officer of a Canadian company called Canadian Visa Expert, and with the same fake email, she presented him with a message that she works within a law firm and consultancy office, and that Karim can immigrate to Canada, and with a review of the texts of the letter, this message was monitored from June last year by the Scamwatcher platform specialized in [monitoring fraud messages](#) for the purpose of immigration, but [Jessica](#) is still working until this year, using the address of the [original company](#).

and this misinformation can be revealed by noting the company's original domain ending with COM and the fake domain that does not exist and ends with net.

Referring to the same email to reveal more facts about it, it was noted that this [email](#) is active in fraud operations, as one of the messages appears in November 2016, that he [wrote](#) to one of the individuals to offer him immigration to Portugal, as well as [another](#) message in 2018 proving the fraud as the sender claims that they are an office located in Los Angeles and provides immigration to Canada.

Mail - Amro Jawahreh - Outlook

REQUISITION FORM 106 - Amro Jawahreh (194011528)

Christine McAllister
To: amrojawahreh@outlook.com
Thu 7/7/2022 8:02 AM

Amro -

Since you've shown interest in our service, I have issued form 106 for your convenience. Simply review and submit it to start your process.

CANADA IMMIGRATION EXPRESS - REQUISITION FORM 106		
INSTRUCTIONS: Review the details in the form and click the "Click to Submit" link at the bottom. You will be redirected to the payment screen where you will be required to pay a symbolic sum to complete your registration and open an application under your name.		
1. REQUISITION DETAILS		
Requisition Date:	Requisition ID:	Requisition Type:
07/07/2022	194011528	Application
2. APPLICANT DETAILS		
Name of Applicant:	Amro Jawahreh	
Email of Applicant:	amrojawahreh@outlook.com	
Date of Birth:	1995-09-29 00:00	
Place of Birth:	Jordan	
Education:	Associates Degree	
Occupation:	Agricultural Engineer	
Original Registration Date:	2022-01-21 11:58:40.07	
Original Registration IP:	5.45.132.47	
3. DECLARATION		
By submitting this form, I hereby declare the following:		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I agree to Canada Immigration Express' Terms of Use I acknowledge that my information will be handled as detailed in Canada Immigration Express' Privacy Policy 		
4. SUBMISSION		
Click the link in the cell to the right to submit this form	Click to Submit	

Christine McAllister →

إلى: ABOBKER.000@gmail.com

REQUISITION FORM 106 - Abubakr Elsheikh (194355756)

الاثنين، ١١ يوليو، ٢٠٢٢ ص ٨٠

Abubakr -

Since you've shown interest in our service, I have issued form 106 for your convenience. Simply review and submit it to start your process.

CANADA IMMIGRATION EXPRESS - REQUISITION FORM 106		
INSTRUCTIONS: Review the details in the form and click the "Click to Submit" link at the bottom. You will be redirected to the payment screen where you will be required to pay a symbolic sum to complete your registration and open an application under your name.		
1. REQUISITION DETAILS		
Requisition Date:	Requisition ID:	Requisition Type:
07/11/2022	194355756	Application
2. APPLICANT DETAILS		
Name of Applicant:	Abubakr Elsheikh	
Email of Applicant:	ABOBKER.000@gmail.com	
Date of Birth:	1992-01-01 00:00	
Place of Birth:	Sudan	
Education:	Completed vocational education/training	
Occupation:	Agricultural Engineer	
Original Registration Date:	2021-09-03 08:42:29.993	
Original Registration IP:	5.245.139.137	
3. DECLARATION		
By submitting this form, I hereby declare the following:		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I agree to Canada Immigration Express' Terms of Use I acknowledge that my information will be handled as detailed in Canada Immigration Express' Privacy Policy 		
4. SUBMISSION		
Click the link in the cell to the right to submit this form	Click to Submit	

Christine McAllister
Public Relations
Canada Immigration Express

Can't see this email properly? [View in browser](#). No longer want to receive my emails? [Unsubscribe](#).

The methods of fraud also amount to the delusion of issuing employment contracts in return for paying an advance fee, and the rest is at the airport, as published by [Cydia Chadi](#) and [Yasmine Zahra](#). This in itself is a unique monument. Referring to the Canadian government platform, it becomes clear that the employer must provide the foreign worker with a copy of a paper called the

[Labor Market Impact Assessment](#) (LMIA), which proves that the employer does not have employees from inside Canada, and that he needs employees from outside it. This paper is one of the requirements for applying for a visa when treated at the embassy, and it is not the same as what happened with [Khadr al-Khatib](#), who was a victim of the monument in the name of employment contracts. Khadr shared a paper he received from one of those who claim to have received an employment contract from the embassy.

When verifying the usefulness of the message received by the fiancé in terms of form and content, it becomes clear that it is forged, as the [original](#) message differs from the forged one in its letterhead (code) with the application number, and it is also sent electronically through the email of the platform of the Canadian Immigration Department, as one of the [electronic forms](#) shows.

تعليق عليه [2]: <https://www.facebook.com/photo?fbid=1038067490246142&set=gm.5426290404153199>

 Employment contract in Canada

 FAIRMONT CANADA
HOTELS & RESORTS

Dear: Khader Alkhatib

your application to work in Canada has been approved. You will be issued a permit declaring your work upon your arrival in Canada after an examination by an official at the Canadian Border Services Agency, subject to your compliance with the requirements of the Immigration and Refugee Protection Act and its regulations. The employee will ask to see this letter and your passport and may ask to see your supporting documents, such as an acceptance letter from the employer. Do not pack these or other valuable papers in your checked baggage. You can learn more about the documents you will need to bring with you by visiting [www.cbsa.gc.ca](#)

As you gather your documents, please take note of the following:

This letter is not a passport or travel document. You will not be permitted to board your flight, even if you have this letter with you.

This letter is not an authorization permitting you to enter or remain in Canada. An officer of the Canada Border Services Agency will make that determination upon your arrival to Canada.

This letter is important because it contains information that will be used by the Canada Border Services Agency to issue your study permit. Please

You must apply for entry to Canada to obtain your work permit by 2023/07/14 (yy/mm/dd). Your passport must be valid after the period in which you intend to stay in Canada. If not, your work permit will not be issued after the expiration date of your passport, or, for US citizens and permanent residents, the expiration date of your identity document. Note: As an international worker in Canada it is your responsibility to ensure that the conditions for your study permit continue to be met, including the requirement to actively pursue employment. Your study permit will automatically become invalid 90 days after you complete the study program, regardless of the expiration date specified on your work permit.

Unique Client Identifier: [REDACTED]

Application Number: [REDACTED]

[REDACTED] KATE MILAN
[REDACTED]
Philippines

[REDACTED] KATE MILAN,

Your application to work in Canada has been approved. A permit authorizing you to work will be issued to you on your arrival to Canada following an examination by an officer of the Canada Border Services Agency, subject to your compliance with the requirements of the *Immigration and Refugee Protection Act* and its Regulations. The officer will ask to see this letter, your passport and may request to see your supporting documents. Do not pack these or other valuable papers in your checked luggage. You can find out more about which documents you will need to bring with you by visiting www.cic.gc.ca/english/work/arriving.asp.

As you gather your documents, please take note of the following:

- This letter is not a passport or travel document. You will not be permitted to board your flight without your passport, even if you have this letter with you.
- This letter is not an authorization permitting you to enter or remain in Canada. An officer of the Canada Border Services Agency will make that determination upon your arrival to Canada.
- This letter is important because it contains information that will be used by the Canada Border Services Agency to issue your work permit. Please do not misplace it.

You must seek entry to Canada to obtain your work permit by 2018/08/08 (yyyy/mm/dd). Your passport must be valid beyond the period you intend to remain in Canada. If not, the validity of your work permit will not be issued beyond the expiry date of your passport, or, for United States citizens and permanent residents, the validity of your identity document.

In this regard, the official on the Immigration and Asylum to Canada Group, the legal advisor [Iyad Al-Basha](#), confirms that there are some consultants who exploit the need of people financially to defraud them, which means that some may face a

real advisor who has a license to practice as a lawyer, but he exploits the need of people to immigrate, and this is what the Canadian government recognized. Therefore, in June 2022, it published a [code of professional conduct for immigration lawyers](#), which clearly included issuing an official receipt to the client for all fees paid to the lawyer, and that the processing of the application should not exceed thirty days.

Indeed, there are those who practice law for fraud, no more and no less. Abu Nour Muhammad contacted [Sayed David](#) in order to obtain immigration, along with his family, to the State of Ontario, Canada. David confirmed to them through an email that they accepted the immigration program in exchange for paying \$10,000 for the immigration application fees. When viewing those documents that were sent to him, it becomes clear that the paper that included the immigration acceptance letter itself contains a discrepancy in the lines and darkening them. However, the address mentioned in the paper is not real.

As for the mail that Abu Nour Mohammed received about the payment information, with scrutiny on its content that the [place](#) of [transfer](#) of the [amount](#) is different from the place of work of David as well as the use of the visual identity of the Canadian government, rather this is not an official business as much as it is a fraud, even if the lawyer has an official license, based on the Code of Lawyers issued by the Department of Immigration Canada.

We have created your Immigration file Mr Mohammed Nazar Raheem Almohy of Iraq A12247778 and family(Narjis Basim Mohammed Al-Mnaseer of Iraq A9688094;Wife, Nooralzahraa Mohammed Nazar Almohy of Iraq A15437433;Daughter, Fatimahalzahraa Mohammed Nazar Almohy of Iraq A15472653;Daughter, Jaafar Alsadeq Mohammed Nazar Almohy of Iraq A15437401;Son) by Immigration Act 1982 The State govt visa application has been sent to you to begin your family immigration application. Your application fee approved by Immigration Act 1982 is been expected for completion. Your fee charge is \$1025 as cost of processing. Payment is expected to be paid to the assigned case officer in charge of your case, you are to send the fee by Money Order of MoneyGram or Western Union to be made to your assigned case officer in Canada to process your filled immigration form and also process your immigration file. We expect the payment receipt within Thursday 21 July 2022 to Thursday 28 July, 2022 to begin your processing, and verify your payment in Canada for processing your file.

Name: Kolade Ehinmisan
City: Winnipeg
State: Manitoba
Country: Canada
Zip Code: R3T 3R1

A scanned copy of payment slip is expected to be sent for payment confirmation
NOTE: The unique client identification number at the upper left corner of this letter is your unique identification number for your own protection do not allow anyone other than authorised representative as it provides access to your personal information on your documents and files which will be active in due time.
A copy of the payment slip is to be scanned and sent after payment. After payment has been confirmed your interview date will be fixed and you will be contacted for your interview and medicals. Ensure you go with all necessary documents during your interview and medicals, payment slip should be included in your documents because it will be the first requirement you will be expected to provide before interview and medicals commence. We expect your arrival soon.

Citizenship and Immigration Canada

Among the misinformation about immigration to Canada, [Mohammed Al-Delbi](#) published in the group "[Immigration News to Belarus and Europe](#)", where he promotes immigration visas to Canada through the Express Entry program without qualifications. Al-Delbi is not a single case of this type of misinformation by mixing fact with fiction. Many preceded him in other groups, but this is not the case, as the granting of visas related to rapid entry is done only through linguistic and professional [qualifications](#).

How late?

The phenomenon of searching for ways to migrate or asylum in the world of the Internet in general and social media in particular is not the result of the moment, as the Google Trend Index shows that the search for the term "[asylum](#) or migration" witnessed a high rate between 2004 and 2008, that is, in the period in which social media began to appear before publicity, and the top five countries in which the results of the search for asylum and migration were: Lebanon, Syria, Jordan, Iraq, Saudi Arabia.

As for the popularity of the term on social media, by referring to the platform of the XNetwork [search](#) tool, it turns out that YouTube occupies the first place by 50%, followed by Twitter and then

Facebook, and the same is true when searching for the term "migration".

The phenomenon of illegal immigration and its promotion through the forgery of documents, or the smuggling of people, whether through [free platforms](#) or social media, continues to spread strongly in recent years, amid unsatisfactory efforts to combat it by those in charge of those platforms.

